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COMMISSIONED REPORT

‘Data matters’:

Report on the Towards a National
Collection Discovery Projects focus group on
data management, documentation, and
archiving practices in digital cultural
heritage projects

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Ashleigh Hawkins, The National Archives
Anna-Maria Sichani, University of London

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	1
1. Introduction	3
The focus group meeting	4
2. TaNC Discovery Projects’ Approaches to Data Documentation, Archiving and Publication	6
2.1 Congruence Engine	6
2.2 Our Heritage, Our Stories	9
2.3 The Sloane Lab	11
2.4 Transforming Collections	13
2.5 Unpath’d Waters.....	14
3.Challenges	15
4. Values	18
5. Recommendations	19
6. Limitations	23
7. Acknowledgements	24
Appendix A - Focus Group Agenda	25
Appendix B - Summary of Guest Presentations	26

Executive Summary

With the increase in digitisation and datafication of cultural heritage over the past few decades, cultural heritage data has become a potentially valuable resource for knowledge production that has been heavily invested in by both public and private investments. It has, however, thus far been under-utilised, with several barriers existing that prevent its reuse. One significant barrier is the lack of clear records or descriptions of how data has been created, collected and processed - also known as data documentation - and standardised methods for recording, managing, maintaining and sharing this information. In summer 2024, representatives of the Towards a National Collection (TaNC) Discovery Projects attended a focus group to discuss and exchange experiences, challenges and potential solutions on issues around data documentation, processing, archiving and publication.

This report presents the key findings and recommendations that developed out of these discussions, and outlines the primary challenges in data management and documentation identified by the five TaNC Discovery Projects, including:

- Accessing data that can be reused is a complex and time-consuming process. Datasets used and created by projects often are not openly available, increasing barriers to their future reuse.
- Insufficient documentation of how data was created, collected or processed makes it difficult to understand, and analyse data.
- Ongoing reassessment of data-related decisions, requires continuous resources to refine or change processes.
- Creating documentation to capture datasets and to document decision-making processes is resource-intensive (financial, time, knowledge and skill).
- Establishing and maintaining the necessary infrastructure to store, analyse and share data is resource intensive, and a lack of centralised infrastructure leads to wasted resources and unnecessary environmental impacts.
- Data focused tasks are frequently undertaken on an ad-hoc basis, often without the involvement of dedicated data specialists, leading to inefficiencies and potential gaps in expertise.

This report makes recommendations to the TaNC Programme, UKRI-AHRC, and the wider cultural heritage and research communities that address project planning, budgeting, and recruitment, as well as the need for advocacy of robust data documentation and management practices, and for centralised investment in data infrastructure(s).

Key recommendations for future projects and investments in this area include:

- **Ensure access to openly available and good-quality data:** Readily accessible high-quality cultural heritage datasets should be made available for computational and research use through the adoption of interoperability standards, comprehensive documentation processes, and open licensing frameworks.
- **Advocate for comprehensive data documentation:** Comprehensive while flexible and customisable data documentation following existing best practices in the field, including the documentation of decision-making processes, is a crucial aspect of project legacy, and

will enable responsible data use and transparency as cultural heritage datasets are increasingly being used also in AI-driven processes.

- **Develop robust data management provision:** Data management planning should be an on-going, dynamic process throughout the project, documenting in a transparent and accessible way decision-making, costs, long-term maintenance and responsibility for the management of data.
- **Invest in sustainable data infrastructure:** Centralised data infrastructure solutions will ensure sustainability, security, maintenance and accessibility of data and data-related outputs beyond a project's end date and thus impact positively on the wider research and cultural heritage communities.
- **Invest in the human side of data infrastructure:** Projects where data is central should involve data specialists and Research Software Engineers from the planning phase to avoid ad-hoc decision-making as a project progresses. Development of data management skills within project teams should be a measured outcome of each project and made available to all team members.

These recommendations are underpinned by a proposed set of shared values for data-focused work which provide a suggested framework for future projects. These values emphasise that data-related work and practices are crucial parts of the research ecosystem:

- **Maintain transparency throughout data processes:** Ensure transparency at every stage of the data lifecycle, from ingestion and management to analysis and sharing. A transparent work ethos is key to maintaining integrity for long-term access to data.
- **Invest in people:** Investing in data-related roles is essential for ensuring the responsible management, preservation, and accessibility of data throughout its entire lifecycle. We advocate for greater encouragement and support towards a 'training as infrastructure' approach to enhance the data-related skills of cultural heritage professionals and researchers.
- **Focus on environmental sustainability:** Data practices should carefully balance the benefits with concern for climate impact. Sustainable data practices, such as optimising storage, using energy-efficient technologies, and incorporating transparent policies that account for the environmental costs of data processes.

1. Introduction

This report stems from a focus group that was initiated in spring 2024 by Anna-Maria Sichani (Congruence Engine) and Ashleigh Hawkins (Our Heritage, Our Stories) mainly as a forum to discuss and exchange experiences, challenges and potential solutions on issues around data documentation, processing, archiving and publication, as they developed in TaNC Discovery projects.

Our work and data practices happen in a particular moment in the history of GLAMs (Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums) and digital cultural heritage. In recent years, movements such as the open movement and open licensing,¹ and Open GLAM have been gaining momentum. These movements have advocated for the creation of open data in cultural heritage by promoting the FAIR Data Principles (which stands for Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable),² as well as for enactment of the CARE Principles (Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics) and Indigenous Data Governance in order to improve discovery, ensure sustainable access, and promote better sharing and reuse.³ More recently, the Collections-as-data movement has been focusing on responsible development and computational use of digital or born-digital cultural heritage collections by highlighting concerns about diverse forms of collaboration among stakeholders, ethical stewardship, social and technical interoperability, transparent documentation, preservation commitment and responsible operations.⁴ In relation to the mission of Collections-as-Data, especially in light of data-driven AI developments, a series of initiatives has been introduced to combat the lack of documentation of cultural heritage data by producing datasheets⁵, data envelopes,⁶ and paradata.⁷ This has been done with the intention of providing context and transparent information on provenance, purposes, composition, the collection process, recommended uses, and biases reflected in cultural heritage datasets, alongside a number of checklists and guidelines to help cultural heritage institutions incorporate documentation practices into their regular activities.⁸

The TaNC programme had a strategy in place (and has recently been developing a set of internal guidelines) to support open and sustainable publication and archiving of the projects' outputs using

¹ Hamilton, G. and Saunderson, F. (2017). *Open Licensing for Cultural Heritage*. Facet.

² GO FAIR. (n.d). <https://www.go-fair.org>

³ Carroll, S.R., et al. (2020). 'The CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance', *Data Science Journal*, 19(1), p. 43. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-043>.

⁴ Padilla, T., Scates Kettler, H., Varner, S., & Shorish, Y. (2023). Vancouver Statement on Collections as Data. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8342166>.

⁵ Alkemade, H., et al. (2023). 'Datasheets for Digital Cultural Heritage Datasets', *Journal of Open Humanities Data*, 9(1), p. 17. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5334/johd.124>.

⁶ Luthra, M. and Eskevich M. (2024). 'Data-Envelopes for Cultural Heritage: Going beyond Datasheets'. Available at: <https://aclanthology.org/2024.legal-1.9>.

⁷ Cameron, S., Franks P., and Hamidzadeh, B. (2023). 'Positioning Paradata: A Conceptual Frame for AI Processual Documentation in Archives and Recordkeeping Contexts'. *Journal of Computing and Cultural Heritage*. 16, 4. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3594728>.

⁸ Candela, G., et al. (2023). 'A checklist to publish collections as data in GLAM institutions'. *Global Knowledge, Memory and Communication*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/GKMC-06-2023-0195>; Lee, B.C.G (2022). 'The "Collections as ML Data" Checklist for Machine Learning & Cultural Heritage.' Available at: <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2207.02960>.

externally-maintained platforms (Zenodo). But the programme did not centrally provide practical guidance or training on data practices (such as data ingestion, documentation, data preparation, schemas, mapping, as well as storage and maintenance). Given the high diversity of Discovery projects in terms of scope, methodology and data employed or created, the data-related challenges encountered by projects needed to be addressed on a case-by-case and *ad-hoc* basis, allowing only limited room for cross-project discussions and knowledge exchange. Each individual project team has therefore been responsible for developing its own approach.

Despite the unique circumstances and custom-developed approaches of each Discovery project, focus group discussions and this resulting report have highlighted common themes, challenges and experiences, making it evident that **data requirements and data best practices are of vital importance for the development of sustainable UK cultural heritage collections infrastructure**. Furthermore, this report, alongside a number of other TaNC commissioned reports and evidence-based documents, seeks to address how challenges around digital data documentation and management practices at cross-TaNC level can further inform future decisions and investment in UK digital data infrastructure for cultural heritage.

The focus group meeting

The focus group on data documentation, archiving and publication practices was held at the School of Advanced Study, University of London and online on 18th July 2024. It was organised by Anna-Maria Sichani (The Congruence Engine) and Ashleigh Hawkins (Our Heritage, Our Stories), with support from Javier Pereda and Sophie Dietrich from the TaNC Directorate.

The focus group meeting was designed to bring together representatives of each of the five TaNC Discovery projects and members of the TaNC Directorate to enable targeted discussions on data documentation, publication and archiving practices (for Agenda, see Appendix A). Goals for the focus group included:

1. To enable knowledge exchange and sharing of challenges and best practices across projects on data documentation and maintenance, and approaches to the publication and archiving of project outputs
2. To assess and clarify requirements for archiving and publication of project outputs with the TaNC Directorate
3. To produce this report for TaNC around this area of work including a focused set of recommendations based on project experiences

The morning session focused on data documentation practices, with a presentation from Jörg Lehmann, from Berlin State Library, on his work with colleagues on Datasheets for Cultural Heritage Datasets (see Appendix B), and presentations from representatives from each of the Discovery Projects in attendance.

The afternoon session was dedicated to archiving and publication practices, with a presentation from Javier Pereda on Digital Preservation for TaNC Projects (see Appendix B), followed by a whole group discussion.

Participants included:

Youcef Benkheda, Our Heritage, Our Stories, University of Manchester

Scott Carballo, Unpath'd Waters, Glasgow School of Art

Ewan Hannaford, Our Heritage, Our Stories, University of Glasgow

Ashleigh Hawkins, Our Heritage, Our Stories, The National Archives

Jörg Lehmann, Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin

Javier Pereda, TaNC Programme, Historic Environment Scotland

Anna-Maria Sichani, The Congruence Engine, University of London

Foteini Valeonti, The Sloane Lab, University College London

Katerina Webb-Bourne, The Congruence Engine, The Science Museum

2. TaNC Discovery Projects' Approaches to Data Documentation, Archiving and Publication

Each TaNC project (with the exception of Transforming Collections) presented their specific approaches to data documentation, archiving and publication. In the following sections we introduce the key points raised in these presentations, the challenges each project faced and how these are being addressed, and future work remaining to the projects.

2.1 Congruence Engine

Anna-Maria Sichani presented on behalf of [Congruence Engine](#)⁹ (CE). She highlighted the central place of data practices within the concept of 'Social Machine' that underpins the project as a dynamic collaboration between people, data and machines. CE's responsible data and data ethics commitments have been conceived and performed as embedded project practice and have further enabled experimental, iterative and self-reflective data practices throughout the project, also in line with the project's action research methodology. She presented the challenges associated with the variety of data used and created by the project, as well as the iterative practices developed around documentation, archiving and publication of the project's data.

Variety of data categories, variety of challenges:

The Congruence Engine project had to deal with various non-uniform data categories, with different requirements regarding their documentation, access and archiving provision.

- The project gathered diverse cultural heritage datasets from project partners through - not always straightforward - ingestion mechanisms, including sending data-rich CSV files by email or even sharing data through a hard drive. These cultural heritage datasets as well as other datasets created within the project were then used for the project's investigations. They required bespoke solutions for their secure storage, curation, documentation, access status and processing.
- Although agreements with partner institutions were in place and an 'as open as possible approach' was promoted by both AHRC and CE, the specific copyright and licensing status and digital systems policy of some datasets limited some reuse or allowed conditional reuse (e.g. for research purposes only without allowing the open publication of the dataset per se). Data access and reuse were often further complicated by some partners' cautious approach towards opening up their collections-as-data, especially for experimental AI-enabled processes, even within a research framework.
- During investigations, the project's core technical experimentation mechanisms, code and other data-driven outputs were developed that, in turn, needed to be documented and maintained, as distinct, accessible and reusable research outputs.

⁹ Congruence Engine Project Website: <https://www.sciencemuseumgroup.org.uk/projects/the-congruence-engine>

- Many documents and data-related resources have been created as ‘paradata’ throughout the project, from meeting minutes, communication channels (Notion, BaseCamp) to guidelines and decision-making documents, requiring specific provisions for their sustainable archiving.

‘Good enough’ data:

Often, we came across and had to document weaknesses, inconsistencies and biases present within externally provided datasets. We established a ‘good enough’ status for the datasets in order for them to be further processed while exploring empirically the practices, politics and the ethics behind historical data cataloguing in UK collections.

Dynamic, accessible and sustainable data documentation:

The team developed a multi-layered approach to data documentation using different practices and systems to store information at multiple points in the data flow, including basic text (ReadMe.md or .txt) files at ingestion stage, a dataset database for management purposes, datasheets at investigation level in order to capture more detailed information regarding the creation, provenance and (re)use of datasets, and finally a CE Data Register, powered by Wikibase, as a proof-of-concept to experiment with semantically-enabled linkage of the datasets.

Short- and long-term archiving solutions:

The project had to balance priorities, needs and resources to make decisions regarding short-term and long-term storage and archiving solutions for its datasets and data-driven outputs. A mixed approach was adopted, using commercial solutions for day-to-day data storage, sharing and access (Box, MicrosoftSuite) and institutionally-enabled, open solutions for more permanent archiving needs (GitHub, SMG open institutional repository, Zenodo).

Challenges:

- **Slowly developing data management strategy:** At the beginning, the project didn’t have a comprehensive, overarching, data management and archiving strategy in place. The DH Research Fellow was given the task of data oversight.
- **Bridging data literacy divides:** Although the project has developed a training programme to support team members and project partners to leverage digital skills, most interest has been towards emergent technologies (GenAI, Computer Vision) and task/tool-specific or data-intensive training, with data management and data literacy skills acquisition being less popular.
- **Beyond traditional research outputs:** The project used and developed diverse data-related outputs (e.g. datasheets, paradata, code). Although there is some reluctance in the academic and GLAM communities more generally to think of such outputs as distinct research outputs or even publications, as manifested by the [HiddenRef](https://hidden-ref.org/) initiative,¹⁰ this was not the case in CE. The project explored and employed ways to establish these as impactful research outputs and roles (via DOIs, citation mechanisms, credit attribution, etc.).

¹⁰ The Hidden REF Website: <https://hidden-ref.org/>.

- **Generous and ethical credit attribution:** the project introduced and embraced an inclusive approach to credit attribution when it comes to data publication and authorship by acknowledging individuals and roles via the adoption of the [CRediT – Contributor Roles Taxonomy](#).¹¹

Future Directions:

Two key open questions remain for CE to resolve:

- How can we ensure better visibility, dissemination and reuse of the project’s data-related outputs to the wider research and GLAM community?
- In what ways can the findings and lessons learned from CE and the rest of the TaNC projects help shape the data infrastructure requirements for a UK cultural heritage collection?

¹¹ Contributor Roles Taxonomy (CRediT) Website: <https://credit.niso.org/>.

2.2 Our Heritage, Our Stories

Ashleigh Hawkins presented on behalf of [Our Heritage, Our Stories](#).¹² She highlighted the challenges associated with documenting living datasets created by other institutions, and decisions around archiving and publication which continue to emerge within the project.

Project Data Complexities:

Our Heritage, Our Stories is aggregating and enriching publicly available heterogeneous datasets of descriptive metadata relating to community generated digital content (CGDC). These datasets, the project's core data, pass through multiple organisations, being modelled, and transformed. Subsets of data are created and re-combined with earlier datasets to create additional ones, and different subsets of data will be made publicly accessible via multiple endpoints in different formats. Because of the inclusion of personal data and the legal obligation to comply with [The Data Protection Act 2018](#),¹³ there is a need to assess the data to make (and document) risk-based decisions and to put in place processes that support data management for as long as the data is available. Additional types of data are created by the project, including interview and focus group transcripts and administrative data.

Layering of Data Documentation:

Datasets are documented at multiple points in the data flow, starting with initial assessment documentation prior to a dataset being shared with the project. This includes Personal Data Risk Rating Documentation, a 'Master Spreadsheet' documenting all interactions with community archives and datasets shared, datasheets for each dataset received and created, and data cards for each dataset created by the AI Lab. Project datasheets are modelled on the recommendations in "Datasheets for Digital Cultural Heritage Datasets", and informed by a template developed by Congruence Engine, with additional facets added to meet project specific needs (version history, language, dataset structure, personal and sensitive data).

Challenges:

- Ad-hoc approach: The project has not developed an overarching data management plan, but an ad-hoc approach to data management and documentation has emerged.
- Lack of knowledge: Detailed documentation of datasets is often undertaken retrospectively, with some understanding of the datasets being lost in the interim. This is exacerbated by datasheets for datasets created by community archives being produced by project members, rather than those involved in the creation of the original data, leading to gaps in knowledge, and a lack of detail and nuance. Although this has been a conscious decision to not burden participating often resource-poor community archives with additional tasks, as a result, we have had to compromise on the level of detail documented.
- Living documents for living datasets: datasheets need to be regularly updated as additional information is uncovered about the data, or the dataset changes, either through processing by the project team or through a request from the data provider.

¹² Our Heritage, Our Stories Project Website: <https://ohos.ac.uk/>.

¹³ The Data Protection Act, 2018: <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2018/12/contents>.

These changes may continue to be made after the research project finishes so there needs to be a process for maintaining up-to-date datasheets that capture the datasets as they evolve.

Archiving and Publication:

The project is governed by UKRI conditions requiring technical project outputs to be available for three years following the project's end date. Project Data Sharing Agreements and Data Protection Impact Assessment guide the approach, based on type of output:

- The Observatory, as the user interface, will be sustained to provide access to modelled enriched data for three years. The public-facing static website will be archived by the University of Glasgow.
- Source and enriched modelled datasets, and all subsets, will be deleted three years after project completion where required by Data Sharing Agreements. Project databases, documentation and research datasets will be stored in the University of Glasgow or Manchester's research data and e-print repositories. These will be deleted after three years, apart from interview and focus group data which will be anonymised and archived.
- Project code and data models will be made available as open-source code/open data, either via GitHub, or an institutional repository of a partner organisation
- Project reports and whitepapers will be published to Zenodo. Peer-reviewed journal articles will also be published based on work in the white papers.

Future Directions:

We will create documentation for additional datasets and undertake an assessment of how FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) source and modelled enriched datasets are.

Outstanding questions to be addressed regarding what will happen beyond January 2028:

- Will we publish dataset documentation, currently created for internal data management purposes, as a legacy of the project?
- Are we going to web-archive The Observatory?
- Would it be possible to retain and re-use some of the datasets the project has curated and created beyond this date?

2.3 The Sloane Lab

Foteini Valeonti presented on behalf of [The Sloane Lab](#).¹⁴ Foteini particularly highlighted concerns around ensuring a continued, accessible, and re-usable legacy of digital project outputs, and discussed some of the challenges the project team have been facing in ensuring these can be maintained beyond the term of the project.

Project Legacy:

The Sloane Lab project team have been proactive in considering the legacy of their project from its inception, focusing on ensuring the accessibility of their outputs beyond the project's lifespan. To ensure this legacy extends beyond research papers, they plan to build a Docker Container to store the project's full technical stack and complete setup, including their Knowledge Base with all its datasets. This would allow people in the medium-long term future to rebuild the Knowledge Base application and access the project's data.

Post-Grant Availability of Outputs:

As the project nears its end, the team is prioritising ensuring the availability of outputs beyond the term of the project's grant. To do so, they have had to secure funding for hosting and licensing.

- The primary expense is hosting the project's Knowledge Base, for which they have managed to secure funding for a couple of years.
- The secondary expense is the licence for Metaphacts, the platform on which the [Sloane Lab's Knowledge Base](#)¹⁵ runs. The team are in discussions with Metaphacts to maintain this licence long-term, and are also exploring transitioning to a licence-free and open-source alternatives for sustainability reasons.

Dissemination and Public Engagement:

The team has been focusing on no-cost measures to ensure the legacy of the project, specifically, dissemination. The project team have published over 10 repositories using the MIT licence, containing code, standalone outputs like parsers, the data model, and other outputs that could be transferable to other projects. They have also launched a [YouTube channel](#)¹⁶ to share all the videos produced during the three years of the project, including lectures, seminars, and tutorials.

Challenges:

The main project-specific challenge has been dealing with IP constraints, as not all datasets they worked with are open licence (CC-0). This limits possibilities for dissemination and future reuse. A cross-project challenge endemic to all research projects is the sharp funding deadline, which is not compatible with limited possibilities of purchasing technology upfront and the need to build flexibility into the project.

¹⁴ The Sloane Lab Project Website: <https://sloanelab.org/>.

¹⁵ Sloane Lab Knowledge Base: <https://knowledgebase.sloanelab.org/resource/Start>.

¹⁶ Sloane Lab YouTube Channel: <https://www.youtube.com/@SloaneLab>.

Future Directions:

The team has been exploring decentralised storage infrastructures for long-term storage deals, with the paper “Decentralising Digital Humanities: Exploring blockchain technology and Web 3 for the Sloane Lab and Towards a National Collection” to be published soon. Although the infrastructure is not yet available, the research found great potential in this area for Digital Humanities in the longer term, with technologies such as blockchain rapidly developing and hopefully providing benefits in the near term.

2.4 Transforming Collections

Representatives of the [Transforming Collections](#)¹⁷ (TC) project were not able to attend the focus group, however, Professor Mick Grierson has kindly provided an overview of their project's approach.

Project Data:

At the start of the TC project we were mindful of the legal and infrastructural issues surrounding data use and access, in particular due to the way our investigation problematised forms of representation within collections and archives. Our project has sought to develop new techniques to decolonise archives using Machine Learning (ML). Specifically, this meant using existing collections from partners, including Tate, Wellcome Collection, Art UK, and a number of other collection owners. Therefore, we understood explicitly that although publicly available data was available for us to use for the purposes of conducting our research, we would have to work hard with partners to reach agreements regarding what we might use, and had a dedicated team in year 1 and 2, including academic data ethics experts, working closely with partners on agreements. More sensitive data in and around collections would take longer to access.

Approach:

Given that it was clearly the case that institutions had sensitivities around certain forms of non-public data, our approach was to instead attempt to design a platform which would allow them to analyse their own data, rather than to allow us access to their data to do the same. This led to the co-development of a research method aiming to provide access to ML tools to those without technical expertise.

Outcomes:

Our approach is interdisciplinary, using co-research methods to help professionals train ML systems to recognise bias through real-world examples, without requiring them to understand ML itself. Through research workshops with TC teams and GLAM stakeholders, we've studied how they identify bias and designed ML tools to support this. This led to development of a unique Interactive Machine Learning (IML) prototype that allows non-experts to create custom text and image analysers, trained with a small set of examples. Recently, this has resulted in deeper collaboration with Tate and potential new partnerships.

¹⁷ Transforming Collections Project Website: <https://www.arts.ac.uk/uai-decolonising-arts-institute/projects/transforming-collections>.

2.5 Unpath'd Waters

Scott Carballo presented on behalf of [Unpath'd Waters](#).¹⁸ He presented the core data set curated by the project from diverse sources, the data generated and archived by the project, and the data-related challenges they faced.

Project Data:

The core data set, curated and maintained by the Archaeology Data Service at the University of York, consists of data aggregated from the four national heritage bodies and local heritage repositories. This data is aggregated in the [Unpath Portal](#),¹⁹ which makes the heritage data searchable in multiple ways, and links to the original source or provider. Additionally, each work package within the project uses and creates its own datasets based on their specific aims and research fields, including design sessions, focus groups, audio-visual records, computer code, and Virtual Reality projects, all of which need to be archived.

Initial Challenges:

Initial challenges included separate approaches to, and standards of, archiving data in heritage institutions across the Four Nations. Different metadata structures adopted in heterogeneous data sources, low data quality and varying levels of granularity across different platforms make data interoperability challenging. Progress has been made in processing and archiving the data to increase interoperability through harmonisation with the ARIADNE ontology, and adoption of the Medin metadata structure.

Current Issues:

Current issues include: difficulties in searching meaningfully through the metadata due to missing search terms in the metadata and the use of controlled vocabularies and time periods which can remove nuance and make search more difficult; the absence of richer content included in the original data but not captured in the core data set; and challenges in navigating through tabs and data pages in the immersive systems created.

Future Directions:

The project aims to adhere to the FAIR Data Principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse of data sets) and increase interoperability through common standards and vocabularies by being part of ARIADNE and Medin.

¹⁸ Unpath'd Waters Project Website: <https://unpathdwaters.org.uk/>.

¹⁹ Unpath Portal: <https://unpathd.ads.ac.uk/>.

3.Challenges

Discussions throughout the focus group highlighted a number of challenges that were common across TaNC Discovery projects, including:

Securing data is a complex process: Gaining access to several important data sets that have previously been agreed in the bid was a complex process, involving ‘boutique’ or large-scale digitisation, rights negotiations with cultural heritage institutions or private companies, and sophisticated or custom-made ingestion set-ups. Theoretically, working with existing digitised data should be simpler than generating new digital data from scratch. However, the absence of Application Programme Interfaces (APIs) often made the transfer of data more complex and/or labour intensive than need be, were APIs available.²⁰

Furthermore, the processing of many of these digitised datasets are restricted by obscure copyright terms or data protection, locked behind paywalls, or their sharing hasn’t yet been technically possible. For many projects, it wasn’t possible to have their datasets in place, or even identified, from the start of the project and a significant amount of staff time and energy has been spent on securing datasets. Similar claims around limited readily available cultural heritage datasets have been raised also from another AHRC-funded project, *Living with Machines*,²¹ and highlighted by a TaNC commissioned report around copyright within UK collections.²²

Available data is of problematic status: There are often no established persistent identifiers (PIDs), or community of use around some of the cultural heritage datasets that we have been using, as they are not openly available to researchers and are sufficiently commercially sensitive they must be stored in a Trusted Research Environment (TRE). That brings challenges of legacy, and how we share derivative datasets or enhancements to datasets that are not open, and the impact this has on the reproducibility of our research and its engagement. The advantages of using, and recommendations to use, PIDs for cultural heritage data were highlighted by The Heritage Connector, Practical Applications of IIF and Persistent Identifier (TaNC Foundation) Projects,²³ and emphasised by participants of the focus group.

²⁰ Indeed, The Heritage Connector Project reported “The availability of museum collection catalogues and other data sources as well-documented application programming interfaces (APIs) significantly speeded up the project’s technical work.” Pg 14. Whereas, the Making it FAIR (Covid-19 Urgency) Project documented the challenges that small cultural heritage institutions face in providing access to data, recommending that storage space in trustworthy digital repositories should be freely available to smaller institutions as part of future infrastructure for the digital humanities. Pg 2.

Stack J. et al. (2022). ‘Final Report - Foundation Projects: Heritage Connector: Transforming text into data to extract meaning and make connections’. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6022678>; Richards, J. et al. (2021). ‘Final Report - Covid 19 Projects: Making it FAIR: Understanding the lockdown ‘digital divide’ and the development of UK digital infrastructures.’ Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5846220>.

²¹ Ahnert R, Griffin E, Ridge M, Tolfo G. (2023). *Collaborative Historical Research in the Age of Big Data: Lessons from an Interdisciplinary Project*. Cambridge University Press. P 24.

²² Wallace, A. (2022). ‘A Culture of Copyright: A scoping study on open access to digital cultural heritage collections in the UK’. Available at: <https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4323683>. P 5.

²³ Stack J. et al. (2022). ‘Final Report - Foundation Projects: Heritage Connector: Transforming text into data to extract meaning and make connections’. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6022678>; Padfield, J. et al. (2022). ‘Final Report - Foundation

Creation of barriers due to absence of documentation: Barriers persist in understanding the data we receive due to the absence of documentation when a dataset is shared. While it is possible to piece together more technical aspects of a dataset's history, knowledge of its context of creation and subsequent use, and the silences and biases within the dataset is usually held only within the institution that created the dataset. Developing awareness of silences in the data and recognising who/what has been silenced is crucial for the ethical (re-)use of such datasets. However, this effort is hampered by the lack of documentation, which risks perpetuating the silencing of minoritised voices.

Documentation of datasets beyond metadata: The need to document datasets beyond metadata seemed to be well understood across projects. This includes documenting the context behind a dataset's creation and the collection it represents, the documentation of how and why certain data was selected or excluded, and documentation of biases and assumptions. While this would further demonstrate transparency, such documentation is not often captured because it requires additional time, effort and skills, and there is uncertainty about the appropriate methodology for documenting this type of information.

Documentation beyond datasets: Participants felt there was value in documenting data beyond core datasets to include decision-making and internal project documents which help to document the inner-workings of the project - what is known in social sciences as 'paradata'. These may not be fully captured in project final reports, but there is currently no methodology for archiving and making such documents publicly accessible. Zenodo was suggested for further exploration.

Documenting decision-making: Transparency on the methodology around data management and the documentation of decision-making could be a more important research output than the actual decisions made. Such documentation of decision-making would also enable better understanding of the needs of research communities with regards to data, how cultural heritage data is being used and why it may be being excluded, and what data is seen as meaningful and usable for inclusion in research.

Data practices are far from linear: Data-related choices and decisions were often viewed as iterative and dynamic processes within the projects. These processes involved assessing data needs, testing and implementing solutions, and then communicating the proposed solution, getting buy-in, experimenting with what that actually looked like in practice, and adjusting data practices accordingly. Each step required time and resources, and transition or change was not always straightforward.

Absence of data plan engenders lack of trust: Some projects found that the absence of a clear and detailed plan on how data would be used and managed within a project created difficulties in developing trust with partner institutions, especially when the use of AI was proposed. This limited engagement and prevented the inclusion of certain datasets.

Projects: Practical applications of IIF as a building block towards a digital National Collection.' Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6884885>; Kotarski, R. et al. (2022). 'Final Report - Foundation Projects: Persistent Identifiers as IRO Infrastructure'. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6359926>.

Data (as) infrastructure: Establishing and maintaining the infrastructure - including hardware, software, services, policies, and more - needed to store, analyse and share data among team members and beyond was a central challenge of many of the projects. All these systems and practices were required to be in place from early on in order for the project teams to be able to conduct their research. However, there is a manifested waste of resources, environmental impacts, and sustainability risks to build and then archive or abandon this type of data infrastructure in every funded project.

Determining responsibility: As time, space and labour are limited resources in the research data-verse, questions arise around the determination of who is responsible for documenting and managing data in cross-institutional projects and whether these decisions are predefined (e.g. in the project bid), or negotiated throughout the course of the project as project structures and processes emerge. Tensions exist as research funding structures necessitate the former approach, but (re-)negotiation over the course of a project better reflects the reality where responsibilities and roles develop, and things not initially envisaged emerge.

'Hidden' data-focused roles: There are projects where data-focused tasks have been performed ad-hoc by existing members of the project team without asking for a specialist appointment such as a data curator, data steward or data rights manager.

4. Values

Our work and recommendations are underpinned by a shared set of values which, although embedded (either implicitly or explicitly) within each of the TaNC Discovery projects, were able to be enacted to differing extents. These values provide a suggested framework for future projects, through which we acknowledge data-focused work and practices as crucial parts of the research ecosystem we live in and perform.

Maintain transparency throughout data processes

Ensure transparency at every stage of the data lifecycle, from ingestion and management to analysis and sharing. This includes clearly assessing and communicating how data is gathered, stored, and used, as well as providing accessible documentation and open communication to foster trust and accountability across all parties involved. Transparency helps all stakeholders understand decision-making and the ethical considerations involved, promoting responsible use and stewardship of cultural heritage data. A transparent work ethos is key in order to maintain integrity for long-term access to data.

Invest in people

Investing in data-related roles is essential for ensuring the responsible management, preservation, and accessibility of data throughout its entire lifecycle. Working with large-scale digital cultural heritage collections requires a multitude of data skills to oversee the quality, security, and ethical access to and use of data, ensuring compliance with legal and institutional guidelines, technical integrity of the data as well as its provenance. We advocate for greater encouragement and support towards a 'training as infrastructure' approach, by enhancing cultural heritage professionals and researchers with ongoing training and skills needed to handle emerging technologies, address challenges related to data privacy, and maintain transparency in data practices.

Focus on environmental sustainability

Data practices should carefully balance the benefits with concern for climate impact. Data practices have a significant environmental impact due to the energy required for data storage, processing, and transmission, as well as the physical infrastructure required (data centres) for all these processes. Sustainable data practices, such as optimising storage, using energy-efficient technologies, and incorporating transparent policies that account for the environmental costs of data processes, can encourage more responsible use of digital resources.

5. Recommendations

Based on discussions at the focus group and the collective experiences of Discovery Projects we recommend the following five recommendations:

Recommendation 1: Ensure access to openly available and good quality data

Securing data: Projects should not underestimate the amount of time and other resources that will be required to identify, secure, and ingest datasets from institutions who have already agreed to participate in the project. Projects should provide funding to institutions providing data where technical work will be required to prepare and export datasets, including for the development of APIs to enable data export at scale. The implications of copyright and data protection for future reuse and access to enriched and derivative datasets should be at the forefront of data selection considerations and discussions. Furthermore, the adoption of an open licensing requirement supporting the publication of all outputs, including data-related ones, created with infrastructure funding via open licences (CC BY) and public domain tools (CC0) for future UK digital collections research infrastructure across TaNC, AHRC and UKRI funding, should be prioritised, as already highlighted by a TaNC commissioned report.²⁴ This will secure data availability from the outset and will significantly reduce barriers encountered by research projects seeking to partner with GLAMs and looking for readily available high-quality cultural heritage datasets.

Working toward data quality and access: Future infrastructure investment should be focused on the development and implementation of 'minimum viable dataset requirements', following a comprehensive data style guide and set of protocols and standards for interoperability for cultural heritage data. Existing foundational work done through the TaNC Foundation projects (specifically regarding adopting PIDs and IIF) can be leveraged.²⁵ Furthermore, to ensure the availability of large pools of quality data, the concept and practice of '[data space for cultural heritage](#)',²⁶ as introduced by the EU, should be explored, as should the diverse 'as a service' processes and infrastructures, such as the [European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage](#) in development as part of the European Union and UKRI funded ECHOES Projects, to enable the exchange and (re)use of data with the appropriate governance mechanisms.²⁷

²⁴ Wallace, A. (2022). 'A Culture of Copyright: A scoping study on open access to digital cultural heritage collections in the UK'. Available at: <https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4323683>. P 3.

²⁵ Kotarski, R. et al. (2022). 'Final Report - Foundation Projects: Persistent Identifiers as IRO Infrastructure'. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6359926>; Padfield, J. et al. (2022). 'Final Report - Foundation Projects: Practical applications of IIF as a building block towards a digital National Collection.' Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6884885>; Stack J. et al. (2022). Final Report: Heritage Connector: Transforming text into data to extract meaning and make connections. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6022678>.

²⁶ Common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage Website: <https://www.dataspace-culturalheritage.eu/en>

²⁷ ECHOES: European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage Website: <https://www.echoes-ecch.eu/>

Developing awareness of data biases and positionality: Projects need to develop an informed approach towards data ethics: to reflect on and develop an understanding of the biases not only inherent in the datasets they work with but also those that are introduced through data selection and documentation processes within the project and epistemological biases within a given knowledge infrastructure. Also, data practices are not performed in a historical or organisational vacuum, usually reflecting the background, politics, and beliefs of the responsible subjects and stakeholders.

Breaking data silos: Leveraging existing linked open data frameworks and infrastructure, as well as embedding interoperability standards in data-driven practices, will contribute towards breaking down cultural heritage data silos and unleash the full potential of data by ensuring it is accessible, shareable, and usable across the wider cultural heritage and research communities, enabling greater collaboration and innovation.

Recommendation 2: Advocate for comprehensive data documentation

Advocating for data documentation: Recipients of grant funding in cultural heritage are in a unique position where they can advocate for, and demonstrate the benefits of, the documentation of cultural heritage data. They should raise awareness of data analysis and documentation methodologies, provide training and allocate funding for institutions providing data for the creation of adequate documentation, and, through their own documentation, provide an example of good practice in a way that is reusable and adoptable for other groups.

Positioning documentation as project legacy: Data documentation should be iterative, continuing throughout the term of a project and beyond. As advocated for by Datasheets for Cultural Heritage Data,²⁸ documentation needs to be standardised but in a way that maintains flexibility and customisability.²⁹ With adequate resources, data documentation can be positioned as a legacy of the project, providing schemas, mappings and documentation of the data used and created even after the data itself is no longer accessible. Furthermore, this type of documentation will be a necessary step to ensure responsible data and transparency are in place as we enter an AI-intensive era also in cultural heritage and Arts and Humanities research.

Exploring methodologies to document decision-making: A research question that extends well beyond the TaNC programme remains concerning the gap between the documentation, archiving and publication of outputs, and that for processes. Future projects should explore methodologies to document risk-based decision-making and the extent to which paradata may help address this gap.

²⁸ Alkemade, H., et al. (2023). 'Datasheets for Digital Cultural Heritage Datasets', *Journal of Open Humanities Data*, 9(1). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5334/johd.124>.

²⁹ This need was previously highlighted by the Preserving and Sharing Born Digital and Hybrid Objects (TaNC Foundation) Project, which called for further commissioning of research into the development of consistent standards for documentation to help develop better understanding of how born-digital objects rely on multi-part systems, networks and infrastructures. Pg 14. Kane, N. et al. (2022). 'Preserving and Sharing Born Digital and Hybrid Objects Across the National Collection.' <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7144616>.

Recommendation 3: Develop robust data management provision

Developing robust data management plans: A robust data management plan should be developed at the project planning phase and maintained as a live document throughout the course of a project, with ownership of the plan identified for as long as the data remains available/accessible. Good data management and documentation practices should be positioned not only for administrative purposes but also as a means of building trust and relationships with partner institutions and demonstrating transparency to stakeholders.

Budgeting for maintenance's unknown costs: Costs for the long-term storage of data, and maintenance of tools and software are generally not known at the project planning stages and often exceed what is anticipated. More than is thought to be required should be budgeted for costs associated with the maintenance of data and infrastructure post-project delivery, as required by the grant conditions, especially given that data-intensive technologies and systems are continually evolving and the cost of related infrastructure, software and tools is often not known at the project planning stages. Projects should be transparent about the costs and decision-making associated with this long-term maintenance to inform future project planning.

Determining responsibility as on-going process: Questions of data ownership, curation and maintenance should be top priority to clarify at the planning stage of a project, identifying where responsibility lies for the tasks of data documentation and management. Responsibility should be reassessed as cross-institutional relationships develop and responsibilities alter throughout a project's course.

Recommendation 4: Invest in sustainable data infrastructure

Identifying sustainable repositories: It should be decided on a project-by-project basis whether a specific digital output is best suited to be published to Zenodo or GitHub (or elsewhere) rather than a centralised decision. However, infrastructure investment should be made towards developing sustainable mechanisms to host, maintain and secure access to data-related outputs (datasets, dataset databases, datasheets, data models) from data-intensive work in cultural heritage. These outputs are usually short-lived (within the usual post 3-years after project period) and as they fall outside the traditional publications' realm, they usually do not meet the criteria to be published via an institutional repository. Furthermore, these data-related outputs require ongoing curation, updated documentation and active dissemination, which will ensure their further reuse by the cultural heritage and research community.

Investing in a centralised infrastructure: Centralised investment is needed to develop more sustainable provision for data storage, to provide mechanisms to support research with digital collections, to enable wider access to and reuse of their digital outputs, and to scale up digital data infrastructure that specifically meets the needs of cultural heritage data.

Recommendation 5: Invest in the human side of data infrastructure

Professionalising data-related roles in interdisciplinary teams: Projects where data is central should involve data specialists and Research Software Engineers from the planning phase to avoid ad-hoc decision-making as a project progresses. Additionally, data management and documentation tasks should be explicitly assigned to specific team members or roles while recognising and valuing all teams' contributions and the diverse types of work involved in producing project outputs.

Building data skills as project legacy: Data management skill development within project teams should be a measured outcome of each project and made available to all team members. Such upskilling could be a valuable legacy of a project, enabling team members to take these skills into future research.

Raising awareness in research assessment of data work: By introducing documentation of project methodology (paradata) and data documentation as alternative research outputs and professionalising data-related roles, projects can productively contribute to new frameworks of assessing research excellence, such as the HiddenRef, with research datasets and research teams to be among the [candidate categories](#) that are vital to research but often overlooked by traditional research evaluations.³⁰

³⁰ The Hidden Ref: Submission Categories 2024: <https://hidden-ref.org/details-of-submission-categories/#Research-Datasets-and-Databases>.

6. Limitations

The focus group on which this report is founded, was held in the final few months of the TaNC Programme, with the report itself not being published until the end of it. As a result, it has not been possible for projects to put many of the recommendations into practice.

The focus group was organised with little notice which resulted in limited participation. While four out of five projects were represented, no principal or co-investigators were able to attend, resulting in significant knowledge of the projects' planning, delivery and decision-making processes not being captured in this report.

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Appendix A - Focus Group Agenda

Cross-TaNC Focus Group on Data Documentation, Archiving and Publication

Focus Group Agenda

Date: 18th July 2024

Location: MakerSpace, School of Advanced Studies, University of London, and online

Facilitators:

Ashleigh Hawkins (Archival Metadata Specialist, The National Archives - Our Heritage, Our Stories)

Anna-Maria Sichani (Post-doctoral Research Associate, SAS - Congruence Engine)

Schedule

11-11.30 **Introduction** - goals for the workshop

11.30-13.30 **Session 1: Data documentation for digital cultural heritage data : challenges, practices and recommendations**

11-30-12 Jörg Lehmann - Datasheets for Digital Cultural Heritage Datasets
presentation

12-13 TaNC projects presentations (10 mins per project)

13-13:30 Whole group discussion - challenges, ethics, recommendations

13:30-14.00 Lunch break

14.00-15.30 **Session 2: Archiving and publication practices for digital cultural heritage data and TaNC outputs**

14:00-14:30 Javier Pereda - TaNC reporting requirements and Zenodo reporting guidance

14:30-15:00 Small group discussion - practical steps/decisions required for TaNC, best practice recommendations for future 'towards a national collection' work

15:00-15:30 Feedback to group and discussion

15.30-16:00 **Closing remarks** - next steps

Appendix B - Summary of Guest Presentations

Datasheets for Cultural Heritage Datasets - Jörg Lehmann

As a framing to the focus group, Dr Jörg Lehmann, post-doctoral researcher in the Digital Humanities based at the Prussian Cultural Heritage Foundation and Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin, presented the work that he and collaborators have been doing to advocate for and develop guidance for the use of datasheets for cultural heritage datasets, as published in [Datasheets for Digital Cultural Heritage Datasets](#).³¹ This initiative is motivated by the desire to more broadly disseminate datasets from cultural heritage institutions for use in machine learning and to develop trust between the two domains. It aims, through datasheets, to address the need to better document cultural heritage datasets and enable datasets to cross from the cultural heritage domain to machine learning.

Jörg framed this discussion around the issue of trust, citing research undertaken in 2024 by the Prussian Cultural Heritage Foundation which found that, in Germany, cultural heritage institutions engender a lot of trust (behind family and friends only), receiving significant support from the public as a result of reliably fulfilling expectations for centuries, not having lost the trust that they have built up over a long time, and being mission driven, rather than geared towards profit maximisation. He argued that cultural heritage institutions have extensive valuable and authentic (human-created) datasets, advocating datasheets as a means of ensuring the trust engendered by cultural heritage institutions is also maintained for cultural heritage datasets: datasheets are created by trusted persons (cultural heritage professionals, researchers...) who are aware of their own positionality and the context in which a dataset was created and has subsequently evolved, and capture this vital information.

After providing a detailed overview of the different features documented in datasheets, Jörg addressed some of the challenges faced so far, including:

- Interdisciplinarity: integrating the differing expertise of cultural heritage practitioners and data scientists within datasheets; finding common ground with different perspectives on bias, objectivity, and positionality across the cultural heritage and machine learning domains
- Problematic terminology and material, silences in the data, and different approaches to harm mitigation

He concluded by outlining planned future developments, including to create a machine-readable version of the datasheet template and publish a follow-up research article with the feedback and lessons learned so far, before opening the floor for a lively discussion.

³¹ Alkemade, H., et al. (2023). 'Datasheets for Digital Cultural Heritage Datasets', *Journal of Open Humanities Data*, 9(1). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5334/johd.124>.

TaNC Directorate Recommendations for Archiving and Publication - Javier

Pereda

The afternoon session was introduced with a detailed presentation from Javier Pereda, senior researcher from the TaNC Directorate, on recommendations for archiving and publishing outputs using Zenodo. Javier framed his presentation by highlighting the obligations that both the TaNC Directorate and individual projects have for the preservation of outputs. For the TaNC Directorate this includes leading on maintaining the legacy of the projects and preparing for future sustainability, devising a clear exit strategy and benefits realisation strategy to show how resources generated will be maintained beyond the duration of the programme, and publishing all project and commissioned reports. Responsibilities of individual projects, on the other hand, as mandated by the conditions of the grant call, include responsibility for short and long-term data sustainability, and for addressing any legal and ethical issues related to processing data.

Javier proposed that Zenodo be used not only to host all TaNC branded reports (as it is currently used), but also other project outputs, including project datasets, collection datasets, GIT and other repositories, Docker, videos etc. He argued the advantages of using Zenodo for this are that it provides long-term preservation, generates a DOI for each item deposited, and links digital outputs held in various places into one central Zenodo community. This will enable Discovery Project final reports to be richer as it will be possible to cross-reference (using DOIs) other digital outputs that are best placed outside of the final report. Javier emphasised throughout his talk that this approach is not obligatory, but recommended by the TaNC Directorate, and will be developed in conjunction with feedback from projects.